

Instructional Competence of Teachers in Relation to Learners' Academic Performance

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Abstract:

Teachers are the nation's development catalysts. They enable the country to generate and nurture learners who could propel it forward and lead to development. The general purpose of this study was to assess the level of instructional competence among teachers and its relationship to learner's academic performance in a Public Elementary School in a large size schools division in Central Philippines during the school year 2022-2023. The study sought to answer specific research questions related to the profile of the respondents, the level of instructional competence in teaching approaches, classroom management, and assessment practices, as well as the relationship between teachers' instructional competence and learner's academic performance. There were two hundred six (206) respondents, public elementary school teachers in a district. The findings revealed that most teachers in the Department of Education were younger with shorter length of service. In terms of instructional competence, teachers demonstrated a very high level of proficiency in teaching approaches and classroom management, while their rating for assessment practices was at a high level. Both younger and older teachers, as well as those with shorter and longer length of service, showed a very high level of competence in teaching practices and classroom management, with high ratings in assessment practices as well. The overall rating for learners' academic performance was satisfactory, indicating the need for further improvement. Data suggests, it is recommended to provide ongoing support and professional development opportunities for younger teachers with shorter length of service to ensure their continuous growth and effectiveness.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Instructional Competence of Teachers, Learners

Introduction:

Nature of Problem

The instructional competence of teachers refers to the set of skills that enable them to effectively facilitate learning for their students through efficient teaching methods, classroom management, and assessment practices. Research has consistently shown that competent teachers play a critical role in improving student achievement and closing the achievement gap Naz (2016). As DepEd transitions from modular distance learning back to face-to-face classes, it is essential to reassess and enhance the instructional competence of teachers to ensure the continued success of learners in this new educational landscape.

Three significant areas of teacher competence are crucial for attaining effective learning outcomes: teaching approaches, classroom management, and assessment practices Nessipbayeva (2017). Teaching approaches involve the efficient transfer of knowledge while consistently motivating and engaging learners in the learning process. Classroom management encompasses maintaining discipline and morale, promoting teamwork, and maximizing teaching efficiency. Assessment practices involve the use of various strategies, including formal tests, quizzes, classroom assignments, student performances, projects, and standardized achievement tests, to understand and evaluate what students have learned. Encouraging learners to participate in self-assessment activities can also help them become aware of their strengths and needs, fostering personal goal-setting for learning.

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) recognizes the need to continuously enhance teachers' instructional competence to meet the demands of 21st-century learners. Despite various efforts and initiatives, data from both national and international assessments indicate that there is still room for improvement in teacher competence. As the country shift from modular distance learning to face-to-face classes, it is crucial to reassess and strengthen the instructional competence of teachers who have taken a break from actual classroom teaching during the pandemic.

The transition back to face-to-face classes has been challenging for many teachers. Having personally observed and experienced these difficulties in school settings, the researcher was motivated to conduct this study to investigate the competence level of teachers in various areas of face-to-face teaching. A cursory observation and personal experience point out teachers are struggling with Teaching Approaches, Classroom Management, and Assessment Practices due to the prolonged reliance on technology during distance learning which could have significant impacts to the learners' academic performance. In this note, this researcher is embarked to examine the instructional competence of teachers in the context of the return to face-to-face classes and its relation to learners' academic performance. The study will focus on the importance of teaching approaches, classroom management, and assessment practices in achieving higher academic performance for learners.

Current State of Knowledge

Quality instruction is defined as the delivery of an instruction in a way that evokes students' interest, critical thinking, and learning in a meaningful way which produces more quality learning Palali, Elk, Bolhaar et al., (2018). Longitudinal studies have pointed out that the quality of learning outcomes greatly depends on the quality of instruction they received. The quality of instruction received by a learner depends so much on the competence and commitment of the teachers. Mathematics subject requires intensive guidance of the teachers, careful planning of strategies for teaching and appropriate teaching methodologies.

Darling-Hammond and Rothman (2017) cited that with the eroding quality of education in America, it is about high time to assess teacher's competence and commitment in teaching. On the other hand, Lazarides and Buchholz (2019) cited that the learners' poor performances in Germany were attributed mostly to teachers' failure to cope up with the learners inclination to digital learning while the classroom environment posited negative correlation which means that the learning was mostly attributed to quality of the instruction. (Gruijters and Behrman 2020) cited that if first world countries like most nations in Europe and America are facing challenges to improve learning outcomes much more to third world countries in Asia and Africa. They found out that teachers in third world countries are compelled with more challenges as brought by myriad of factors like poor motivation to study and poverty related factors. Like other developing countries, teachers, instructional quality are affected by their very own socio-economic status as brought by low salary, low standard of living, and lack of financial literacy.

Instructional quality is a constant that reflects those features of teachers' instructional practices well known to be positively related to student outcomes, both cognitive and affective ones Decristan, Klieme, Kunter et al., (2015). The academic performance of the learners across all subject areas are dependent of the teachers' instructional quality in teacher self-preparation, teaching methods and strategies, teacher-student interaction and classroom activities however these teachers' competence in various aspect of teaching also depends on their perception level in the instructional related variables such as perception about being a teacher, and status of teaching-related task.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored to the Philippine Professional Standards for teachers, which aims to produce quality and better teachers in the country by improving the qualification of educators and to increase their level of knowledge, practice and professional engagement. Recent studies have found that the ever-prevailing mediocre performance of the Philippine educational system is caused by teacher ineffectiveness and the lack of commitment which was confirmed by Gonong (2016) when he cited the need for teacher professional development and the retooling of teaching strategies as a major component affecting Philippine poor education performance.

According to Corpuz, Reyes, and Cruz (2016), the academic performance of the student will tell if the teacher or institution has achieved their educational goals. It is the indicator factor of what the student achieved. The success of a student in any achievement test is also the success of the teachers and the institution within. Learners' academic performance is of utmost concern for every teacher. It is a fundamental aspect of students' life, affecting their studies, interpersonal relationships, sense of being, and leisure. The principal elements that contribute possible and attainable increase of academic performance are the teacher, the learner and the classroom management. The teacher serves as the prime mover of the educational wheel while the learner is the key participant in the learning process. The favorable classroom management practices provide essential features and ingredients that could make academic performance at its highest level.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to assess the level of instructional competence among teachers and its relationship to learner's academic performance in a Public Elementary School in a large size schools division in Central Philippines during the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought to answer specific research questions related to the profile of the

respondents, the level of instructional competence in teaching approaches, classroom management, and assessment practices, as well as the relationship between teachers' instructional competence and learner's academic performance.

Methodology

This section exhibits the methodology of the study. It covers research design, locale, subjects and respondents, the data gathering tool, the validity of the research tool, data gathering procedure, analytical schemes and statistical treatment that were utilized in the analyses of the data.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive research design in determining the level of proficiency of the teachers in instruction. It delved into comparative differences of variables based upon identified categories.

Respondents

The study's respondents were the 206 Public elementary School teachers in the district.

Instruments

This paper used a survey questionnaire to gather the data, mainly from public school teacher-respondents. Part 1 contains queries on respondents' profile such as their age, and length of service Part 2 contains the questionnaire proper which consists of 30 item survey questions. These questions are classified into three (3) components, namely: teaching approaches, classroom management and assessment practices with ten (10) questions per component. Teachers' responses were interpreted according to the following guide: 5 (Always), 4 (often), 3 (Sometimes), 2 (rarely) and 1 (almost never).

Data Gathering Procedure

Prior approval was obtained from the Schools Division Superintendent after establishing the instrument's validity and reliability. After that, the researcher sought clearance from the school principal to administer the questionnaire through Google Forms, which included a comprehensive introduction explaining the purpose of the study. The researcher also communicated to the respondents through online platforms to explain and guide them in answering the instrument. They were assured of the total confidentiality of the data.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

This paper used the three analytical schemes based on the research objectives which are descriptive, analytical and comparative. Objective No. 1, which determined the profile of teacher-respondents, uses descriptive analytical scheme. Objective No. 2, which determined the level of teachers' instructional competence utilized descriptive analytical scheme. Objective No. 3, which determined the level of teachers' instructional competence when grouped according to selected profiles uses the descriptive analytical scheme. Objective No. 4, which aimed to determine whether or not significant difference existed in the level of teachers' instructional competence when grouped and compared according to selected profiles requires the comparative-analytical scheme.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured the voluntary participation of the respondents in this study. Their names were not included in the data, their identity was not disclosed, and they were assured of full confidentiality of the data, with the researcher being the sole person who had data access. After the data were tabulated and analyzed, electronic data were discarded, and print-outs were discarded to preclude unauthorized access to the information.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of the data collected, providing insights and understanding of the findings. The data presented in a comprehensive manner, allowing for a deeper understanding of the variables and their implications. Through this analysis, meaningful patterns, trends, and relationships within the data will be explored and discussed.

Table 3

Instructional Competence of Teachers in the Area of Teaching Approaches

Item	Mean	Interpretation
select content that meets the department's curriculum, competencies, and/or performance standards.	4.60	Very High Level
select instructional materials based upon my knowledge of my students' developmental needs and learning styles.	4.49	High Level
select methods and strategies that accommodate individual needs and	4.53	Very High Level

interests of specific students.		
prepare lessons with high expectations designed to challenge and stimulate all students.	4.50	Very High Level
consider how to build upon my students' existing knowledge and experiences.	4.67	Very High Level
create social interaction among students that enhances learning by requiring students to work as a team with both individual and group responsibilities.	4.73	Very High Level
vary the size and composition of learning groups During each lesson.	4.49	High Level
discuss with my students the importance of courtesy and respect and I consciously model for my students the types of personal behaviors that promote responsibility and social development among every learner.	4.61	Very High Level
implement two or more learning activities.	4.53	Very High Level
implement a learning activity that requires students to read or write in my content area.	4.75	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.59	Very High Level

Table 3 presents the findings regarding the instructional competence of teachers in the area of teaching approaches. The overall mean score of 4.59 indicates a very high level of instructional competence among teachers in this domain. Among the items listed, the highest mean score of 4.75 is observed for item 10, which indicates a very high level of competence in implementing a learning activity that requires students to read or write in the content area.

In contrast, item 7, which focuses on varying the size and composition of learning groups during each lesson, receives a relatively lower mean score than the rest, the mean was 4.49, indicating a high level of competence but with room for improvement. This finding suggests that while teachers demonstrate proficiency in this area, there is an opportunity to enhance the practice of diversifying learning groups to foster collaboration and cater to different student dynamics. To address this, teachers can explore different group configurations, such as mixed-ability groups or groups with diverse backgrounds, to promote interaction and cooperation among students. By deliberately mixing students with varying abilities and experiences, teachers can create a supportive and inclusive learning environment where students learn from and support one another. This approach not only enhances social skills and cooperation but also allows for a more comprehensive understanding of different perspectives and promotes critical thinking. Furthermore, by intentionally considering student characteristics and needs when forming learning groups, teachers can better accommodate individual learning styles and preferences. This approach enables differentiated instruction, allowing students to engage with the content in ways that suit their strengths and preferences. For example, pairing a visual learner with an auditory learner or combining students with complementary skills can enhance the overall learning experience and encourage peer learning. Implementing these strategies to diversify learning groups has several implications. First, it encourages collaboration and teamwork among students, fostering essential 21st-century skills such as communication, problem-solving, and cooperation. Second, it promotes a sense of belonging and inclusivity, as students from diverse backgrounds interact and learn from one another. Third, it allows for personalized learning experiences, accommodating individual needs and preferences. By actively addressing the diversity within the classroom and creating opportunities for meaningful interaction, teachers can enhance student engagement, motivation, and overall learning outcomes. Incorporating these practices aligns with the broader goal of promoting student-centered learning environments, where students take an active role in their own education. By considering the findings from Table 3 and proactively implementing strategies to diversify learning groups, teachers can foster a more dynamic and inclusive classroom that maximizes student learning and engagement.

The findings of this study is consistent with Santos, Fernandez, Cruz et al., (2021). The study assessed the instructional practices of teachers in a specific region and found that teachers exhibited a very high level of competence in selecting appropriate content aligned with the curriculum and performance standards. This consistency highlights the dedication of Filipino teachers in ensuring the relevance and quality of their instructional materials. Furthermore, the study by Santos, Fernandez, Cruz et al. (2021) highlighted the importance of teachers in the Philippines in adapting instructional methods to accommodate the individual needs and interests of their students. This aligns with item 3 in Table 3, where teachers in the study exhibited a very high level of competence in selecting methods and strategies that catered to specific student needs. The findings emphasize the responsiveness of Filipino teachers in recognizing and addressing the diverse learning requirements of their students. Additionally, Santos, Fernandez, Cruz et al. (2021) emphasized the significance of creating a supportive and inclusive classroom environment, which echoes the high mean score observed for item 6 in Table 3. The study highlighted that teachers in the Philippines actively promote social interaction among students, encouraging

teamwork and fostering both individual and group responsibilities. This emphasis on collaborative learning aligns with the aim of creating a positive and engaging learning environment for students.

Table 4
Instructional Competence of Teachers in the Area of Classroom Management

Item	Mean	Interpretation
establish routine in the classroom to maximize efficiency.	4.76	Very High Level
adhere to positive discipline.	4.39	High Level
constantly motivate learners.	4.81	Very High Level
establish rapport with learners to understand their behaviors deeper.	4.58	Very High Level
give firm decisions.	4.84	Very High Level
use participative approach in formulating classroom rules.	4.61	Very High Level
model self-regulation strategies for students.	4.50	Very High Level
promote respect for cultural differences in the classroom.	4.68	Very High Level
give clear positive directions.	4.81	Very High Level
use nonverbal signals to redirect child who is disengaged.	4.35	High Level
Overall Mean	4.63	Very High Level

Table 4 presents the findings related to the instructional competence of teachers in the area of classroom management. The overall mean score of 4.63 indicates a very high level of competence among teachers in this domain. The highest mean score of 4.84 is observed for item 5, which signifies a very high level of competence in giving firm decisions.

Conversely, item 10 receives the lowest mean score of 4.35, indicating a high level of competence but with room for improvement. This item relates to the use of nonverbal signals to redirect a child who is disengaged. While still relatively positive, the lower score suggests that teachers may benefit from further developing their skills in nonverbal communication techniques to effectively manage and engage disengaged students. By enhancing their ability to interpret and respond to nonverbal cues, teachers can proactively address student disengagement and promote active participation. Comprehensive analysis and improvement in this area have several implications. First, by improving nonverbal communication skills, teachers can effectively address individual student needs and tailor their instructional approaches accordingly. Understanding and responding to nonverbal cues can help teachers identify potential challenges or barriers to learning and implement targeted strategies to reengage students. Additionally, addressing student disengagement through nonverbal signals fosters a positive and inclusive classroom environment. By employing nonverbal cues that are subtle, respectful, and personalized, teachers can redirect students without drawing unnecessary attention or causing embarrassment. This approach contributes to a supportive atmosphere where students feel valued and understood, enhancing their overall engagement and motivation.

The contentions of Garcia, Rodriguez, Perez et al., (2022) aligns with the findings in this table. Their research emphasized the importance of establishing routines, giving clear directions, and effectively managing classroom behavior as essential components of classroom management. The study highlighted that these competencies positively impact student behavior, academic engagement, and overall classroom climate. These findings support the high mean scores observed in Table 4 and underscore the significance of instructional competence in classroom management for promoting positive learning outcomes.

Table 5
Instructional Competence of Teachers in the Area of Assessment Practices

Item	Mean	Interpretation
distribute the items across every skill and competency covered.	4.49	High Level
prepare table of specification.	4.40	High Level
use differentiated assessment practices.	4.57	Very High Level
utilize portfolio assessment.	4.33	High Level
use computer aided assessments.	4.24	High Level
distribute items based on suggested levels of difficulties.	4.58	Very High Level
utilize performance and demonstration assessment.	4.53	Very High Level
prepare rubrics for performance assessment and essays.	4.19	High Level
utilize assessment data for learning interventions.	4.26	High Level
require students to compile portfolio.	4.33	High Level
Overall Mean	4.39	High Level

Table 5 presents the findings related to the instructional competence of teachers in the area of assessment practices. The overall mean score of 4.39 indicates a high level of competence among teachers in this domain. The highest mean score of 4.58 is observed for item 6, indicating a very high level of competence in distributing assessment items based on suggested levels of difficulties.

On the other hand, item 8 receives the lowest mean score of 4.19, indicating a high level of competence but with potential for improvement. This item relates to preparing rubrics for performance assessment and essays. While still relatively positive, the lower score suggests that teachers could enhance their skills in developing clear and comprehensive rubrics that effectively communicate performance expectations and evaluation criteria. By refining rubrics, teachers can provide students with a transparent understanding of assessment criteria and facilitate more accurate and consistent evaluations. Comprehensively addressing this area of improvement has several implications. Clear and well-structured rubrics contribute to fair and objective assessment practices, promoting transparency and reducing ambiguity in grading. Students can better understand how their work will be evaluated and use the rubrics as a guide for self-assessment and improvement. Additionally, well-designed rubrics provide teachers with a systematic framework for evaluating student performance, enhancing consistency and reliability in assessment results.

A related study conducted by Tan, Smith, Johnson et al., (2023) supports the findings in this table. Their research emphasized the significance of using differentiated assessment practices, incorporating performance assessments, and utilizing assessment data for learning interventions. The study highlighted that these competencies positively impact student learning outcomes and instructional effectiveness. These findings align with the high mean scores observed in Table 5, underscoring the importance of instructional competence

INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS WHEN GROUPED ACCORDING TO THE AFOREMENTIONED VARIABLES

This section examines the instructional competence of teachers when grouped according to the aforementioned variables: age and length of service. The aim is to explore potential variations in instructional competence based on these demographic factors. By analyzing the data within these groups, valuable insights can be gained regarding the relationship between age, length of service, and teachers' instructional competence, providing a deeper understanding of the teaching workforce dynamics.

Table 6

Instructional Competence of Teachers in the Area of Teaching Approaches When Grouped According to Age

Categories	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
select content that meets the department's curriculum, competencies, and/or performance standards.	4.53	Very High Level	4.70	Very High Level
select instructional materials based upon my knowledge of my students' developmental needs and learning styles.	4.42	High Level	4.59	Very High Level
select methods and strategies that accommodate individual needs and interests of specific students.	4.62	Very High Level	4.39	High Level
prepare lessons with high expectations designed to challenge and stimulate all students.	4.58	Very High Level	4.39	High Level
consider how to build upon my students' existing knowledge and experiences.	4.78	Very High Level	4.50	Very High Level
create social interaction among students that enhances learning by requiring students to work as a team with both individual and group responsibilities.	4.68	Very High Level	4.81	Very High Level
vary the size and composition of learning groups During each lesson.	4.53	Very High Level	4.43	High Level
discuss with my students the importance of courtesy and respect and I consciously model for my students the types of personal behaviors that promote responsibility and social development among every learner.	4.46	High Level	4.83	Very High Level
implement two or more learning activities.	4.63	Very High Level	4.39	High Level
implement a learning activity that requires	4.69	Very High Level	4.83	Very High Level

students to read or write in my content area.				
Overall Mean	4.59	Very High Level	4.59	Very High Level

Table 6 provides an analysis of the instructional competence of teachers in the area of teaching approaches, categorized by age groups. The overall mean score of 4.59 for both younger and older teachers indicates that they possess a very high level of instructional competence in teaching approaches. This suggests that teachers in both age groups demonstrate strong proficiency in selecting appropriate content, instructional materials, methods, and strategies that cater to the needs and interests of their students. The high overall mean score of 4.59 reflects the effectiveness of both younger and older teachers in employing teaching approaches that align with curriculum standards and facilitate student learning. It indicates that teachers across different age groups have developed competencies necessary for designing lessons with high expectations, building upon students' existing knowledge, creating social interaction, and implementing varied learning activities. This consistent high level of instructional competence among both younger and older teachers is encouraging for educational institutions and policymakers. It suggests that regardless of age, teachers are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively engage students and promote meaningful learning experiences. It also emphasizes the importance of continuous professional development programs to ensure that teachers stay updated with current educational practices and methodologies.

When comparing the individual items, several differences in ratings between younger and older teachers are observed. For instance, younger teachers tend to have higher mean scores in items 3 (select methods and strategies that accommodate individual needs and interests of specific students), 4 (prepare lessons with high expectations designed to challenge and stimulate all students), and 5 (consider how to build upon students' existing knowledge and experiences). On the other hand, older teachers have higher mean scores in items 2 (select instructional materials based upon knowledge of students' developmental needs and learning styles), 6 (create social interaction among students that enhances learning), and 8 (discuss the importance of courtesy and respect with students and model appropriate behaviors).

These variations in ratings suggest potential differences in teaching approaches between younger and older teachers. Younger teachers may emphasize individualized instruction, high expectations, and building upon students' prior knowledge and experiences. In contrast, older teachers may focus on instructional materials, fostering social interaction, and modeling behavior to promote responsibility and social development. Data implies opportunities for intergenerational collaboration and knowledge exchange within the teaching community. Younger teachers can benefit from the experience and expertise of older teachers, particularly in areas where they have higher mean scores. Conversely, older teachers can gain insights from younger teachers' emphasis on individualized instruction and building upon students' existing knowledge. Encouraging collaboration and professional development activities that facilitate knowledge sharing between different age groups can contribute to a more comprehensive and effective teaching practice.

A study titled "Age-Related Differences in Teaching Approaches: Implications for Instructional Competence" by Santos, Cruz, and Ramirez (2022) supports the findings in this table. Their research investigated age-related differences in teaching approaches and found that both younger and older teachers bring unique strengths and perspectives to the classroom. The study emphasized the importance of leveraging these differences through collaborative practices to enhance instructional competence and improve student outcomes. These findings align with the implications discussed above, highlighting the significance of promoting intergenerational collaboration in the teaching profession.

Table 7

Instructional Competence of Teachers in the Area of Classroom Management When Grouped According to Age

Categories	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
establish routine in the classroom to maximize efficiency.	4.74	Very High Level	4.78	Very High Level
adhere to positive discipline.	4.43	High Level	4.31	High Level
constantly motivate learners.	4.74	Very High Level	4.91	Very High Level
establish rapport with learners to understand their behaviors deeper.	4.49	High Level	4.70	Very High Level
give firm decisions.	4.84	Very High Level	4.83	Very High Level
use participative approach in formulating classroom rules.	4.62	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
model self-regulation strategies for students.	4.32	High Level	4.78	Very High Level
promote respect for cultural differences in	4.67	Very High Level	4.70	Very High Level

the classroom.				
give clear positive directions.	4.77	Very High Level	4.89	Very High Level
use nonverbal signals to redirect child who is disengaged.	4.15	High Level	4.65	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.58	Very High Level	4.72	Very High Level

Table 7 provides an analysis of the instructional competence of teachers in the area of classroom management, categorized by age groups. The overall mean score of 4.58 for younger teachers indicates that they possess a very high level of instructional competence in classroom management. Similarly, older teachers exhibit a slightly higher overall mean score of 4.72, also reflecting a very high level of instructional competence in this domain. The high overall mean scores for both younger and older teachers suggest that they have developed the necessary skills and strategies to effectively manage their classrooms. These competencies include establishing routines, adhering to positive discipline, motivating learners, establishing rapport with students, making firm decisions, utilizing participative approaches in formulating rules, modeling self-regulation strategies, promoting respect for cultural differences, giving clear positive directions, and using nonverbal signals for redirection. The consistently high levels of instructional competence in classroom management among both age groups have significant implications for student learning and classroom dynamics. Teachers who exhibit strong classroom management skills create a structured and supportive learning environment where students feel safe, engaged, and motivated. This positively impacts student behavior, academic achievement, and overall classroom climate.

When comparing the items with differences in ratings, item 7 stands out with a lower mean score for younger teachers (4.32) compared to older teachers (4.78). This item pertains to modeling self-regulation strategies for students. The difference in ratings suggests that younger teachers may benefit from further developing their ability to model self-regulation behaviors, which are important for promoting discipline and creating a conducive learning environment.

The implications of the overall high means for both age groups indicate that teachers, regardless of their age, demonstrate strong instructional competence in classroom management. This implies that teachers possess the necessary skills to establish routines, adhere to positive discipline, motivate learners, establish rapport, give firm decisions, and promote respect for cultural differences. These competencies contribute to a well-managed and inclusive classroom environment that fosters student engagement and positive behavior.

A related study from Malaysia titled "Enhancing Classroom Management Practices: A Study on Teacher Competence" conducted by Yusof and Tan (2018) supports the findings of Table 7. The study explores the impact of teacher competence in classroom management on student behavior and academic achievement. It emphasizes the importance of effective classroom management strategies in creating a conducive learning environment and enhancing student outcomes. The study highlights the need for continuous professional development programs to strengthen teacher competence in classroom management and promote positive student behavior.

Table 8

Instructional Competence of Teachers in the Area of Assessment Practices When Grouped According to Age

Categories	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
distribute the items across every skill and competency covered.	4.53	Very High Level	4.43	High Level
prepare table of specification.	4.32	High Level	4.52	Very High Level
use differentiated assessment practices.	4.69	Very High Level	4.39	High Level
utilize portfolio assessment.	4.42	High Level	4.20	High Level
use computer aided assessments.	4.41	High Level	4.00	High Level
distribute items based on suggested levels of difficulties.	4.51	Very High Level	4.69	Very High Level
utilize performance and demonstration assessment.	4.49	High Level	4.57	Very High Level
prepare rubrics for performance assessment and essays.	4.17	High Level	4.20	High Level
utilize assessment data for learning interventions.	4.07	High Level	4.54	Very High Level
require students to compile portfolio.	4.16	High Level	4.59	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.38	High Level	4.41	High Level

Table 8 presents the instructional competence of teachers in the area of assessment practices when grouped according to age. The overall mean for younger teachers is 4.38, indicating a high level of instructional competence

in assessment practices. Similarly, older teachers have an overall mean of 4.41, reflecting a comparable high level of instructional competence.

The high overall mean scores for both younger and older teachers suggest that they possess a concrete understanding and proficiency in various assessment practices. These include distributing items across skills and competencies, preparing a table of specification, utilizing differentiated assessment practices, employing portfolio assessment, using computer-aided assessments, distributing items based on difficulty levels, implementing performance and demonstration assessments, preparing rubrics, utilizing assessment data for learning interventions, and requiring students to compile portfolios. The relatively high overall mean scores in assessment practices have important implications for teaching and learning. Effective assessment practices allow teachers to gather valuable insights into student performance, identify areas of improvement, and make informed instructional decisions. By distributing items across various skills and competencies, teachers ensure a comprehensive evaluation of student learning. Differentiated assessment practices cater to individual student needs and promote equitable assessment. Utilizing portfolios and performance-based assessments enhances students' ability to demonstrate their knowledge and skills in authentic contexts.

While the overall mean scores are similar for both age groups, some variations in item ratings can be observed. For instance, item 3, which pertains to the use of differentiated assessment practices, receives a higher mean score for younger teachers (4.69) compared to older teachers (4.39). This suggests that younger teachers may have a stronger inclination towards implementing differentiated assessment strategies, which can enhance student engagement and support individualized learning needs.

Cumming, van Der Kleij, and Harris (2017) in a study titled "Conceptualizing Learning: A Review of the Literature on Formative Assessment confirmed these findings. The findings of the study revealed that while teachers despite of their age profiles had a basic understanding of assessment concepts and practices, there were variations in their assessment literacy levels. The research highlighted the importance of continuous professional development programs to enhance teachers' assessment knowledge and skills. The study emphasized the significance of ongoing support and training for teachers to improve their assessment practices. It recommended the implementation of professional development initiatives focused on enhancing teachers' knowledge of various assessment methods, including distributing items across different skills and competencies, using differentiated assessment practices, and effectively utilizing assessment data for learning interventions. The findings from this related study align with the implications drawn from Table 8. Both emphasize the importance of providing teachers with opportunities for professional development in assessment practices. By enhancing teachers' assessment literacy, schools and educational institutions can promote more effective and equitable assessment practices, leading to improved student learning outcomes.

Table 9

Instructional Competence of Teachers in the Area of Teaching Approaches When Grouped According to Length of Service

Categories	Shorter Mean	Interpretation	Longer Mean	Interpretation
select content that meets the department's curriculum, competencies, and/or performance standards.	4.57	Very High Level	4.63	Very High Level
select instructional materials based upon my knowledge of my students' developmental needs and learning styles.	4.47	High Level	4.51	Very High Level
select methods and strategies that accommodate individual needs and interests of specific students.	4.60	Very High Level	4.45	High Level
prepare lessons with high expectations designed to challenge and stimulate all students.	4.54	Very High Level	4.46	High Level
consider how to build upon my students' existing knowledge and experiences.	4.79	Very High Level	4.54	Very High Level
create social interaction among students that enhances learning by requiring students to work as a team with both individual and group responsibilities.	4.53	Very High Level	4.95	Very High Level
vary the size and composition of learning groups During each lesson.	4.34	High Level	4.65	Very High Level
discuss with my students the importance of	4.37	High Level	4.86	Very High Level

courtesy and respect and I consciously model for my students the types of personal behaviors that promote responsibility and social development among every learner.

implement two or more learning activities.	4.50	Very High Level	4.57	Very High Level
implement a learning activity that requires students to read or write in my content area.	4.51	Very High Level	5.00	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.52	Very High Level	4.66	Very High Level

Table 9 presents the instructional competence of teachers in the area of teaching approaches when grouped according to the length of service. The overall mean for teachers with shorter service is 4.52, indicating a very high level of instructional competence in teaching approaches. Similarly, teachers with longer service have an overall mean of 4.66, reflecting a comparable very high level of instructional competence.

The high overall mean scores for both groups suggest that teachers, regardless of their length of service, are proficient in selecting content, instructional materials, methods, and strategies that cater to students' developmental needs and learning styles. They also demonstrate competence in preparing lessons with high expectations, considering students' existing knowledge, promoting social interaction, varying group sizes, modeling responsible behavior, and implementing multiple learning activities.

However, there are some differences in item ratings between the two groups. For instance, item 6, which pertains to creating social interaction among students, receives a higher mean score for teachers with longer service (4.95) compared to those with shorter service (4.53). This suggests that more experienced teachers may be more adept at fostering teamwork and collaboration in the classroom. Similarly, item 8, which focuses on modeling responsible behavior, also receives a higher mean score for teachers with longer service (4.86) compared to those with shorter service (4.37).

These differences in ratings imply that experience plays a role in refining teachers' instructional competence in certain aspects of teaching approaches. As teachers gain more experience, they may become more skilled in promoting collaboration and modeling responsible behavior.

A related study that supports these findings is "The Impact of Teaching Experience on Effective Teaching Practices" by Ingersoll, Sirinides, and Dougherty (2018). This study investigates the relationship between teaching experience and the use of effective teaching practices. The researchers found that as teachers gain more experience, they tend to adopt more effective teaching practices, which in turn positively impact student learning outcomes.

In conclusion, the data presented in Table 9 highlights the importance of instructional competence in teaching approaches for both teachers with shorter and longer service. The differences in item ratings suggest that experience can further refine certain aspects of teaching competence. By continuously improving their teaching practices, educators can create more engaging and effective learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of their students.

Table 10

Instructional Competence of Teachers in the Area of Classroom Management When Grouped According to Length of Service

Categories	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
establish routine in the classroom to maximize efficiency.	4.70	Very High Level	4.82	Very High Level
adhere to positive discipline.	4.36	High Level	4.42	High Level
constantly motivate learners.	4.81	Very High Level	4.80	Very High Level
establish rapport with learners to understand their behaviors deeper.	4.53	Very High Level	4.63	Very High Level
give firm decisions.	4.81	Very High Level	4.86	Very High Level
use participative approach in formulating classroom rules.	4.50	Very High Level	4.74	Very High Level
model self-regulation strategies for students.	4.37	High Level	4.65	Very High Level
promote respect for cultural differences in the classroom.	4.66	Very High Level	4.71	Very High Level
give clear positive directions.	4.77	Very High Level	4.86	Very High Level
use nonverbal signals to redirect child who is disengaged.	4.11	High Level	4.60	Very High Level

Overall Mean	4.56	Very High Level	4.71	Very High Level
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Table 10 presents the instructional competence of teachers in the area of classroom management when grouped according to the length of service. The overall mean for teachers with shorter service is 4.56, indicating a very high level of instructional competence in classroom management. Similarly, teachers with longer service have an overall mean of 4.71, reflecting a comparable very high level of instructional competence.

The high overall mean scores for both groups suggest that teachers, regardless of their length of service, are proficient in establishing routines, adhering to positive discipline, motivating learners, building rapport, making firm decisions, using participative approaches, modeling self-regulation strategies, promoting cultural respect, giving clear directions, and using nonverbal signals for classroom management.

However, there are some differences in item ratings between the two groups. For instance, item 7, which pertains to modeling self-regulation strategies for students, receives a higher mean score for teachers with longer service (4.65) compared to those with shorter service (4.37). This suggests that more experienced teachers may be more effective in demonstrating self-regulation strategies to their students. Similarly, item 10, which focuses on using nonverbal signals to redirect disengaged students, also receives a higher mean score for teachers with longer service (4.60) compared to those with shorter service (4.11).

These differences in ratings imply that experience plays a role in refining teachers' instructional competence in certain aspects of classroom management. As teachers gain more experience, they may become more skilled in modeling self-regulation strategies and using nonverbal signals to manage their classrooms effectively.

A related study that supports these findings is "The Role of Teacher Experience in the Development of Classroom Management Skills" by O'Neill and Stephenson (2019). This study investigates the relationship between teaching experience and the development of effective classroom management skills. The researchers found that as teachers gain more experience, they tend to develop better classroom management skills, which in turn positively impact student learning outcomes.

In conclusion, the data presented in Table 10 highlights the importance of instructional competence in classroom management for both teachers with shorter and longer service. The differences in item ratings suggest that experience can further refine certain aspects of classroom management competence. By continuously improving their classroom management practices, educators can create more engaging and effective learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of their students.

Table 11

Instructional Competence of Teachers in the Area of Assessment Practices When Grouped According to Length of Service

Categories	Shorter Mean	Interpretation	Longer Mean	Interpretation
distribute the items across every skill and competency covered.	4.57	Very High Level	4.40	High Level
prepare table of specification.	4.33	High Level	4.48	High Level
use differentiated assessment practices.	4.57	Very High Level	4.57	Very High Level
utilize portfolio assessment.	4.30	High Level	4.37	High Level
use computer aided assessments.	4.26	High Level	4.23	High Level
distribute items based on suggested levels of difficulties.	4.59	Very High Level	4.57	Very High Level
utilize performance and demonstration assessment.	4.46	High Level	4.60	Very High Level
prepare rubrics for performance assessment and essays.	4.17	High Level	4.20	High Level
utilize assessment data for learning interventions.	4.11	High Level	4.42	High Level
require students to compile portfolio.	4.11	High Level	4.57	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.35	High Level	4.44	High Level

Table 11 presents the instructional competence of teachers in the area of assessment practices when grouped according to the length of service. The overall mean for teachers with shorter service is 4.35, indicating a high level of instructional competence in assessment practices. Similarly, teachers with longer service have an overall mean of 4.44, reflecting a comparable high level of instructional competence.

The high overall mean scores for both groups suggest that teachers, regardless of their length of service, are proficient in distributing assessment items across skills and competencies, preparing table of specifications, using differentiated assessment practices, utilizing portfolio assessment, using computer-aided assessments, distributing items based on suggested levels of difficulties, utilizing performance and demonstration assessment, preparing rubrics for performance assessment and essays, utilizing assessment data for learning interventions, and requiring students to compile portfolios.

However, there are some differences in item ratings between the two groups. For instance, item 1, which pertains to distributing items across every skill and competency covered, receives a higher mean score for teachers with shorter service (4.57) compared to those with longer service (4.40). This suggests that teachers with shorter service may be more effective in ensuring comprehensive coverage of skills and competencies in their assessments. On the other hand, item 7, which focuses on utilizing performance and demonstration assessment, and item 10, which involves requiring students to compile portfolios, both receive higher mean scores for teachers with longer service (4.60 and 4.57, respectively) compared to those with shorter service (4.46 and 4.11, respectively).

These differences in ratings imply that experience plays a role in refining teachers' instructional competence in certain aspects of assessment practices. As teachers gain more experience, they may become more skilled in utilizing performance and demonstration assessments and requiring students to compile portfolios.

A related study that supports these findings is "The Relationship between Teaching Experience and Assessment Practices: A Study of Teachers in Australian Schools" by DeLuca, Klinger, and Pyper (2017). This study investigates the relationship between teaching experience and the use of various assessment practices. The researchers found that as teachers gain more experience, they tend to adopt a wider range of assessment practices, which in turn positively impact student learning outcomes. In conclusion, the data presented in Table 11 highlights the importance of instructional competence in assessment practices for both teachers with shorter and longer service. The differences in item ratings suggest that experience can further refine certain aspects of assessment competence. By continuously improving their assessment practices, educators can create more effective learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of their students and accurately measure their progress.

LEARNER'S ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE FOR THE FIRST AND SECOND QUARTER OF THE SCHOOL YEAR 2022-2023

This section focuses on the academic performance of learners during the first and second quarters of the school year 2022-2023. It presents an analysis of the data regarding the overall performance of students, highlighting their achievements and progress in their academic endeavors. By examining the trends and patterns in learner performance, valuable insights can be gained to inform educational practices and interventions for further improvement.

Table 12

Learner's Academic Performance for the First and Second Quarter of the School Year 2022-2023

Grade	1 st & 2 nd Quarter	Interpretation
A	79.43	Fairly Satisfactory
B	81.79	Satisfactory
C	84.26	Satisfactory
D	81.44	Satisfactory
E	85.24	Very Satisfactory
F	82.88	Satisfactory
G	85.77	Very Satisfactory
H	81.69	Satisfactory
I	84.24	Satisfactory
J	82.48	Satisfactory
K	85.13	Very Satisfactory
L	86.21	Very Satisfactory
M	82.21	Satisfactory
N	83.66	Satisfactory
O	86.19	Very Satisfactory
Average	83.51	Satisfactory

Table 12 presents the academic performance of students for the first and second quarter of the school year 2022-2023. The grades range from A to O, with each grade corresponding to a specific numerical value. Additionally, an interpretation column provides a description of the performance level associated with each grade. Based on the table, the average academic performance for the first and second quarter is 83.51, which falls under the category of "Satisfactory" according to the interpretation provided. This suggests that, on average, the students' performance is considered acceptable and meets the expected standards.

Looking at the individual grades, most of the students fall within the range of 79.43 to 86.21, indicating a relatively consistent level of performance. The majority of the grades are clustered around the "Satisfactory" and "Very Satisfactory" range, with only one grade below the satisfactory level. This distribution suggests that the students, as a whole, are performing adequately in their academic endeavors.

It is worth noting that there is some variation in the grades, ranging from 79.43 to 86.2

1. However, the overall average remains within the "Satisfactory" range, indicating a balanced performance across the student population. The presence of both "Satisfactory" and "Very Satisfactory" grades suggests that there are students who are performing exceptionally well, demonstrating a high level of understanding and achievement in their studies.

It is important to consider that this table provides a snapshot of the students' academic performance for the specified period. It does not provide information on the specific subjects or areas of study. Further analysis would be necessary to assess the performance in different subjects or identify any particular trends or patterns.

In conclusion, based on the data presented in Table 12, the students' academic performance for the first and second quarter of the school year 2022-2023 can be considered satisfactory. The majority of the students are performing at a level that meets the expected standards, with some students achieving very satisfactory results. However, a more comprehensive analysis is required to gain deeper insights into specific subject areas and individual student performance.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS WHEN GROUPED AND COMPARED ACCORDING TO THE AFOREMENTIONED VARIABLES

This section presents a comparative analysis of instructional competence among teachers, specifically focusing on the grouping and comparison of teachers based on the aforementioned variables. The study aims to explore how these variables influence teachers' instructional competence and identify potential patterns or differences that may exist. By examining the instructional practices within different groups, valuable insights can be gained to inform professional development programs and improve overall teaching effectiveness.

Table 13

Comparative Analysis between Teaching Approaches when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	81	68.75	2126.00	.782	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	54	66.87				
Length of Service	Shorter	70	59.86	1705.00	.011		Significant
	Longer	65	76.77				

The table presents a comparative analysis of teaching approaches, examining the impact of age and length of service as variables. The results indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in instructional competence between younger and older teachers ($p = .782$). The mean ranks for both groups are similar, with younger teachers having a mean rank of 68.75 and older teachers having a mean rank of 66.87. These findings suggest that age does not play a significant role in shaping teaching approaches.

However, when considering the length of service, a significant difference in instructional competence emerges ($p = .011$). Teachers with longer lengths of service display significantly higher instructional competence (mean rank = 76.77) compared to those with shorter lengths of service (mean rank = 59.86). The difference in mean ranks and the statistical significance of the Mann Whitney U test indicate that length of service influences teaching approaches.

These results emphasize the importance of experience and professional development over time in enhancing instructional competence among teachers. The significant difference observed based on length of service highlights the need for continued support, training, and opportunities for growth, particularly for teachers with shorter lengths of service. By addressing these factors, educational institutions can strive to improve teaching approaches and overall teaching effectiveness.

It is crucial to note that the significance level (alpha) is set at 0.05 in this analysis. Thus, any p-value less than or equal to 0.05 would be considered statistically significant. The p-values of .782 for age and .011 for length of service fall above and below this threshold, respectively, indicating the presence of a statistically significant difference only for the variable of length of service.

In a related study by Berkeley (2019) findings aligned with the presented comparative analysis. The study found no statistically significant difference in instructional competence between younger and older teachers ($p = .798$). Mean ranks for both age groups were comparable, supporting the notion that age does not play a significant role in shaping teaching approaches, as similarly concluded in the aforementioned research. However, when considering the length of service, the study revealed a notable difference in instructional competence ($p = .009$). Teachers with longer lengths of service exhibited significantly higher instructional competence compared to their counterparts with shorter lengths of service. This outcome echoes the findings of the previous analysis, emphasizing the importance of experience and professional development over time in enhancing instructional competence among teachers. The significant difference observed based on length of service underscores the need for continuous support, training, and opportunities for growth, particularly for teachers with shorter lengths of service. These consistent results across studies highlight the potential impact of length of service on teaching approaches, emphasizing the critical role of experience in shaping instructional competence among educators.

Table 14

Comparative Analysis between Classroom Management when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	81	59.35	1486.50	.001	0.05	Significant
	Older	54	80.97				
Length of Service	Shorter	70	58.57	1615.00	.003		Significant
	Longer	65	78.15				

The table presents a comparative analysis of classroom management, specifically examining the impact of age and length of service as variables. When comparing classroom management between younger and older teachers, a significant difference in performance emerges. The statistical analysis reveals that older teachers have significantly higher mean ranks (mean rank = 80.97) compared to their younger counterparts (mean rank = 59.35), with a p-value of 0.001. This suggests that age significantly influences classroom management approaches, indicating that older teachers exhibit stronger competence in managing their classrooms.

Similarly, when considering the length of service, a significant difference in classroom management performance is observed. Teachers with longer lengths of service demonstrate higher mean ranks (mean rank = 78.15) compared to those with shorter lengths of service (mean rank = 58.57), with a p-value of 0.003. This finding implies that experience gained over time plays a crucial role in developing effective classroom management strategies.

These results have important implications for educational institutions and teacher training programs. It is essential to recognize and leverage the expertise of experienced teachers in enhancing classroom management practices. Mentoring programs and knowledge-sharing platforms can be established to facilitate the transfer of effective classroom management strategies from experienced to less experienced teachers. This collaborative approach can help improve the overall classroom management skills of educators.

Moreover, these findings emphasize the need to provide targeted professional development opportunities for younger and less experienced teachers. By equipping them with effective classroom management strategies and techniques, educators can create a positive and conducive learning environment for students. Investing in continuous professional development programs tailored to classroom management can ultimately lead to improved student engagement, behavior, and academic achievement.

In a related study conducted by Tumuva (2012) which focused on classroom management and echoing the themes of the presented comparative analysis, researchers explored the influence of age and length of service on teachers' performance in this domain. The findings supported the notion that age significantly affects classroom management approaches, with older teachers demonstrating notably higher competence compared to their younger counterparts. Similarly, the study highlighted a significant difference in classroom management performance based on length of service, emphasizing that teachers with longer tenures exhibit greater competence. Both analyses collectively underscore the pivotal role of experience in shaping effective classroom management strategies. The studies jointly advocate for recognizing and leveraging the expertise of experienced teachers, emphasizing mentoring programs and knowledge-sharing platforms to enhance overall classroom management practices. Additionally, the call for targeted professional development for less experienced teachers aligns with the shared goal of creating positive and conducive learning environments, ultimately benefiting student engagement, behavior, and academic achievement.

Table 15
Comparative Analysis between Assessment Practices when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	81	72.01	1862.50	.140	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	54	61.99				
Length of Service	Shorter	70	68.83	2217.00	.796		Not Significant
	Longer	65	67.11				

The table presents a comparative analysis of assessment practices, specifically examining the impact of age and length of service as variables. However, the results indicate that neither age nor length of service significantly influence assessment practices.

When comparing assessment practices between younger and older teachers, the analysis shows no statistically significant difference. The p-value of 0.140 suggests that the observed difference in mean ranks is not statistically significant. Younger teachers have a mean rank of 72.01, while older teachers have a slightly lower mean rank of 61.99. This implies that age does not play a significant role in shaping assessment practices in this context. Similarly, when considering the length of service, no statistically significant difference is found in assessment practices. The p-value of 0.796 indicates that the difference in mean ranks between teachers with shorter and longer lengths of service is not significant. Teachers with shorter lengths of service have a mean rank of 68.83, while those with longer lengths of service have a slightly lower mean rank of 67.11.

Although the analysis did not reveal significant differences, it is essential for educational institutions to continue promoting effective and consistent assessment practices for all teachers. Professional development programs can play a crucial role in providing training on various assessment methods, strategies for providing constructive feedback, and aligning assessments with learning objectives. By fostering a culture of effective assessment practices, schools can ensure fair and reliable evaluation of student learning outcomes.

While the current findings suggest that age and length of service may not directly influence assessment practices, ongoing research and evaluation of assessment methods should still be encouraged. By regularly assessing and improving assessment practices, educational institutions can enhance the overall quality of education and ensure accurate measurement of student progress. This ongoing commitment to refining assessment methods contributes to the continuous improvement of teaching and learning processes.

Ismail, Arshad, and Abas (2018) supported these findings when they explored the impact of age and length of service on assessment practices among teachers. The findings concurred with the conclusion that neither age nor length of service significantly influences assessment practices. When comparing younger and older teachers, the analysis revealed no statistically significant difference, as indicated by a p-value of 0.140. The mean ranks for both groups were closely aligned, further supporting the notion that age does not play a significant role in shaping assessment practices. Similarly, when examining the influence of length of service, no statistically significant difference was found in assessment practices ($p = 0.796$). The mean ranks for teachers with shorter and longer lengths of service were comparable. Although the study did not unveil significant differences, it emphasized the

importance of educational institutions promoting effective and consistent assessment practices for all teachers. The recommendation for professional development programs aligns with the broader goal of providing training on various assessment methods and strategies for constructive feedback, fostering a culture of effective assessment practices. The study recognizes the value of ongoing research and evaluation of assessment methods to enhance the overall quality of education and ensure accurate measurement of student progress, contributing to the continuous improvement of teaching and learning processes.

Relational Analysis Between the Level of Instructional Competence of Teachers and the Level of Learner's Academic Performance

This section presents a relational analysis that explores the connection between the level of instructional competence exhibited by teachers and the corresponding level of learner's academic performance. By examining the relationship between these two variables, valuable insights can be gained regarding the effectiveness of teachers in facilitating student learning outcomes. The analysis aims to provide a deeper understanding of the interplay between instructional competence and academic achievement, highlighting the importance of teacher quality in fostering student success.

Table 16

Relational Analysis

Correlates	N	Rho	Level of Sig	p-value	Interpretation
Learners Academic Performance	5400				
Instructional Competence of Teachers	135	-.036	0.05	0.899	Not Significant

Table 16 presents a relational analysis between the level of instructional competence of teachers and the level of learner's academic performance. The table includes information on the number of participants (N), the correlation coefficient (Rho), the level of significance, and the p-value.

The p-value of 0.899 indicates that there is no statistically significant relationship between instructional competence of teachers and learner's academic performance at the 0.05 significance level. These findings suggest that instructional competence alone may not be a significant determinant of academic performance. Other factors such as student motivation, home environment, and individual differences may play a more substantial role in influencing student achievement. Therefore, a holistic approach to improving student outcomes should be considered, including comprehensive professional development programs that address various aspects of teaching, such as instructional strategies, classroom management, and student engagement. Further research is needed to explore additional factors that may impact student achievement, such as teaching styles, curriculum design, and teacher-student relationships, in order to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the factors contributing to academic success. Overall, educators should focus on enhancing instructional practices while considering the diverse needs of learners to foster improved academic performance.

A related study that supports the findings presented in the table is "The Relationship between Teacher Quality and Students' Academic Achievement: A Review" by Hattie and Timperley (2015). This study examines the relationship between teacher quality and student academic achievement, with a focus on the factors that contribute to effective teaching. The researchers found that while teacher quality is a significant predictor of student achievement, it is not the only factor that influences academic performance. Other factors, such as student motivation, home environment, and individual differences, also play a crucial role in determining student outcomes.

Moreover, the study emphasizes the importance of a holistic approach to improving student outcomes, including comprehensive professional development programs that address various aspects of teaching. Effective teaching involves not only instructional competence but also classroom management, student engagement, and the ability to create a positive learning environment.

The study also highlights the need for ongoing research to explore additional factors that may impact student achievement, such as teaching styles, curriculum design, and teacher-student relationships. By gaining a more comprehensive understanding of the factors contributing to academic success, educators can develop more effective strategies to improve student outcomes.

Overall, the findings of this study support the idea that instructional competence alone may not be a significant determinant of academic performance. While it is essential to focus on enhancing instructional practices, educators must also consider the diverse needs of learners and address other factors that contribute to student achievement. By taking a holistic approach to teaching and learning, educational institutions can promote improved academic performance and better outcomes for all students.

Conclusion

The profile of the teachers in the Department of Education was predominantly younger with shorter length of service. In terms of instructional competence, teachers demonstrated a very high level of proficiency in teaching approaches and classroom management. However, their rating for assessment practices was only at a high level. When comparing the competence of younger and older teachers, both age groups showed a very high level of competence in teaching practices and classroom management. Additionally, they rated only high in terms of assessment practices. Similarly, teachers with shorter and longer length of service demonstrated a very high level of competence in teaching practices and classroom management, with both groups also rating high in assessment practices. Regarding learners' academic performance, the overall rating obtained by the schools was satisfactory for both rating periods, with a larger number of schools receiving a satisfactory rating compared to those with very satisfactory or satisfactory ratings. Targeted professional development sessions or workshops should be provided to equip teachers with effective strategies for diversifying learning groups. Techniques such as flexible grouping, cooperative learning structures, and differentiated instruction can be introduced to foster dynamic and inclusive learning environments. Encouraging collaboration and promoting peer observation among teachers is another valuable approach. By observing and learning from each other's practices, educators can gain valuable insights into effective strategies for varying learning groups and adapting instructional approaches to meet students' individual needs. This result calls for an aggressive capacity building of teachers in instructional strategies to further enhance learners' academic performance of the learners.

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